

Synthesis and crystal structure of cobalt(III) complexes with pyrazine-2,6- and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acids

G. S. Sanyal^{a*}, R. Ganguly^a, P. K. Nath^a and R. J. Butcher^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, India
E-mail : rakesh_ganguly@yahoo.com Fax : 91-33-5828282

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Howard University, Washington, D.C. 20059, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 27 April 2001, accepted 6 October 2001

Complexes of Co^{III} with pyrazine-2,6- and pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acids have been synthesized. The ligands act as tridentate coordinating through the heterocyclic ring nitrogen and two carboxyl oxygens in both the complexes. Single crystal X-ray analyses of both the complexes reveal the structures as distorted octahedral, Co sitting at the center and surrounded by one tridentate ligand and three ammonia. The counter anion is nitrate.

The complexation of metal ions by dipicolinic acid (H₂L) has been extensively studied^{1,2} partly for ability of the ligand to form stable chelates³ with diverse coordination modes such as bidentate, tridentate, meridian or bridging and partly for its biological significance⁴. Six- and seven-coordinate complexes with mononuclear, binuclear and polynuclear structures are also reported¹. In contrast, very little structural study has been done on complexes using isoelectronic pyrazine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (H₂L') although some solution chemistry is there in literature⁵.

Structural studies on the complexes of H₂L with some trivalent metal ions such as Fe^{III}, Mn^{III}, V^{III}, Nd^{III} are well documented^{1-4,6}. A search of the Cambridge Structural Database for dipicolinate complexes with cobalt revealed only the binuclear complex⁷ (μ -4,4'-bipyridyl)-bis(diaqua-(pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylato)cobalt)octahydrate containing a cobalt(II) ion coordinated through the pyridine nitrogen and two carboxylate oxygen donor atoms of a dipicolinate ligand.

In search for a cobaltic analog of the ferric/manganic ion-pair types^{3,6} [Fe(L)(H₂O)₃][Fe(L)₂].6H₂O, [Mn(L)(H₂L)][Mn(L)₂], we initiated synthetic and structural investigation of Co^{III} complexes with dipicolinic acid as well as pyrazine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (Figs. 1 and 2).

This paper describes crystal and molecular structures of monoclinic [Co^{III}(L)(NH₃)₃]NO₃ (**1**) and orthorhombic [Co^{III}(L')(NH₃)₃]NO₃ (**2**).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Results and Discussion

Single crystal X-Ray data of **1** and **2** are given in Table 1 together with refinement details. Selected bond angles and bond distances of **1** and **2** are given in Table 2. Table 3 contains a comparative data of bond distances of various metal complexes with H₂L.

The structures of the cobalt complexes, [Co(L)-(NH₃)₃]NO₃ and [Co(L')(NH₃)₃]NO₃ are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. In both the cases, the cationic species sits on a crystallographic two-fold symmetry passing through C(1), N(1), Co, and N(3). The metal ion is hexacoordinated by two carboxylate O and one N of heterocyclic carboxylic acid and three NH₃ forming a distorted octahedral structure. Two NH₃ molecules occupy axial positions while the third NH₃ along with L are at the equatorial positions. The axial NH₃ molecules are nearly perpendicular to the equatorial plane [**1** : bond angle N(2)-Co-N(1) 91.88(5)°, N(2)-Co-N(3) 88.12(5)°, N(2)-Co-O(1) 91.08(7)°; **2** : N(2)-Co-N(1) 91.74(5)°, N(2)-Co-N(3) 88.26(5)°, N(2)-Co-O(1) 91.38(6)°]. The slight deviation may be due to steric crowding of the bulky heterocyclic carboxylic acid group. The central nitrogen of the nitrate anions sits on a center of inversion and thus the oxygen positions are disordered. The pyridine ring in **1** or the pyrazine ring in **2** retains its approximate C_{2v} symmetry to within experimental error.

Unlike in other bis-dipicolinates of trivalent Fe or Cr, the bonding in the present Co^{III} complex containing the single dipicolinate moiety is rather relieved as evident from the Co-N (1.840(2) Å) and Co-O (1.930(1) Å) distances due to less steric hindrance. The axial NH₃ are at greater distance from the metal [**1** : 1.9481(16) Å; **2** : 1.9477(16) Å] than the equatorial NH₃ [**1** : 1.933(2) Å; **2** : 1.9331(13) Å] as expected.

Note

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for [Co(L)(NH₃)₃]NO₃ and [Co(L')(NH₃)₃]NO₃

	[Co(L)(NH ₃) ₃]NO ₃	[Co(L')(NH ₃) ₃]NO ₃
Empirical formula	C ₇ H ₁₂ CoN ₅ O ₇	C ₆ H ₁₁ CoN ₆ O ₇
Formula weight	337.15	338.14
Temperature (K)	293(2)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Orthorhombic
Space group	C2/c	C222 ₁
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 11.543(2)$ Å $\alpha = 90^\circ$ $b = 10.4821(9)$ Å $\beta = 108.885(16)^\circ$ $c = 10.4450(11)$ Å $\gamma = 90^\circ$	$a = 9.534(3)$ Å $\alpha = 90^\circ$ $b = 11.090(3)$ Å $\beta = 90^\circ$ $c = 10.8166(10)$ Å $\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	1195.8(3) Å ³	1143.7(5) Å ³
Z	4	4
Density (calcd.) Mg/m ³	1.873	1.964
Absorption coeff. mm ⁻¹	1.480	1.550
F(000)	688	688
Crystal size mm ³	0.49 × 0.72 × 0.44	0.32 × 0.88 × 0.36
Theta range for data collection	3.00 to 37.41°	2.82 to 27.51°
Index ranges	-15 ≤ h ≤ 0, -13 ≤ k ≤ 0, -13 ≤ l ≤ 13	-12 ≤ h ≤ 9, -9 ≤ k ≤ 14, 0 ≤ l ≤ 14
Reflections collected	1505	1444
Independent reflections	1436 [R(int) = 0.0122]	1294 [R(int) = 0.0166]
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Data/restraints/parameters	1436/4/135	1294/0/105
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.118	1.073
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R1 = 0.0260, wR2 = 0.0679	R1 = 0.0211, wR2 = 0.0555
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0277, wR2 = 0.0693	R1 = 0.0213, wR2 = 0.0556
Extinction coefficient	0.0132(18)	0.0082(16)
Largest diff. peak and hole eÅ ³	0.309 and -0.266	0.351 and -0.511

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) of [Co(L)(NH₃)₃]NO₃ (1) and [Co(L')(NH₃)₃]NO₃ (2)

Molecule	Bond lengths (Å)				
	1	2			
Co-N(1)	1.8405(19)	1.8287(18)	O(1)-C(4)	1.296(2)	1.289(2)
Co-O(1)	1.9301(12)	1.9331(13)	O(2)-C(4)	1.222(2)	1.227(2)
Co-N(3)	1.933(2)	1.928(2)	C(3)-C(4)	1.508(3)	1.506(3)
Co-N(2)	1.9481(16)	1.9477(16)	C(1)-C(2)	1.391(3)	-
C(3)-N(1)	1.3309(19)	1.3252(19)	N(4)-C(4)	-	1.340(3)
Angles (°)					
Molecule	1	2		1	2
N(1)-Co-N(2)	91.88(5)	91.74(5)	C(3)-N(1)-Co	117.88(11)	118.45(10)
O(1)-Co-N(2)	91.08(7)	91.38(6)	N(1)-C(3)-C(4)	110.82(15)	110.56(16)
O(1)-Co-N(1)	83.03(4)	82.76(4)	O(2)-C(4)-O(1)	124.57(18)	125.71(19)
N(1)-Co-N(3)	180.000(1)	180.0	O(1)-C(4)-C(3)	113.59(14)	113.57(15)
O(1)-Co-N(3)	96.97(4)	97.24(4)	N(1)-C(3)-C(2)	119.33(19)	117.90(18)
N(2)-Co-N(3)	88.12(5)	88.26(5)	O(2)-C(4)-C(3)	121.84(17)	120.72(18)
C(4)-O(1)-Co	114.64(11)	114.53(11)			

Table 3. M-N and M-O average bond distances (Å) and ionic radii (Å) for the iron(III), chromium(III) and cobalt(III) dipicolinate complexes*

Metal(M)	M-N	M-O	Ionic radii
Fe ^{III}	2.05	2.02	0.785 (HS) 0.690(LS)
Cr ^{III}	1.97	2.00	0.755 0.750 (HS)
Co ^{III}	1.84	1.93	0.685 (LS)

*Ref. 14.

Fig. 3. Displacement ellipsoid drawing (20% probability) of $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{L})(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$, showing the atom-numbering scheme.

Carboxylate groups retain their ionicity [1 : O-C-O 124.57(18)°, C-O 1.296(2) Å and C=O 1.222(2) Å; 2 : O-Co-O 125.71(19)°, C-O 1.289(2) Å and C=O 1.227(2) Å] reflecting non-involvement of the COO^- groups in the hydrogen-bonding network.

The unit cell contains four $[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$ units for 1 and four $[\text{Co}(\text{L}')(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$ for 2. The polyhedra in both the complexes are interconnected by H-bonding through NO_3^- and NH_3 . The participation of NO_3^- in the H-bonding is apparent from the elongation of the mean N-O bond length to about 1.267 from 1.22 Å in the gaseous phase.

Experimental

Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (Schuchardt) was used as obtained. Pyrazine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid and $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3$ were prepared by reported methods^{8,9}.

Preparation of metal complexes :

$[\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$ (1) : To $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (250 mg, 1.0 mmol) in water (20 ml) was added pyridine-2,6-dicarboxy-

Fig. 4. Displacement ellipsoid drawing (20% probability) of $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{L}')(\text{NH}_3)_3]^+$ cation, showing the atom-numbering scheme.

lic acid (250 mg, 1.5 mmol) in water (20 ml) when strong effervescence occurred. After complete ceasing of effervescence, the purple coloured solution was concentrated to about one-fourth of original volume. Dark purple coloured crystalline product that separated out was washed with cold water and dried in air. The complex was dissolved in water and kept for a week to grow single crystals (Found : Co, 17.2; C, 24.8; H, 3.8; N, 20.8. $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_3\text{NO}_4)(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$ calcd. for : Co, 17.5; C, 24.9; H, 3.6; N, 20.8%).

$[\text{Co}(\text{L}')(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$ (2) : Procedure was same as 1 (Found : Co, 17.9; C, 21.6; H, 3.0; N, 24.8. $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{NH}_3)_3]\text{NO}_3$ calcd. for : Co, 17.5; C, 21.3; H, 3.3; N, 24.9%).

Cobalt was determined gravimetrically by usual procedure. C, H, N were analyzed in Leco-910 CHNS/O analyzer.

X-Ray crystallography : Crystals were glued to the ends of a thin glass fiber and transferred to a Siemens P4/S diffractometer using $\text{MoK}(\alpha)$ and graphite monochromator. Cell dimensions and an orientation matrix for data collection were obtained from a least-squares refinement of the setting angles of at least 25 accurately centered reflections. The structures were solved by direct methods using the SHELXTL package of computer programs¹⁰. Neutral atom scattering factors were used¹¹ with corrections for real and imaginary anomalous dispersion¹². All structures were refined by full-matrix least-square methods based on F^2 using SHELXTL-96¹³ and used all unique data. Non-hydrogen atoms were located in difference Fourier syntheses and refined isotropically. Additional material available from the authors comprises of hydrogen atom coordinates, complete set of bond distances and angles, atomic coordinates and anisotropic displacement parameters.

Note

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.G.) is thankful to the University of Kalyani for a Fellowship.

References

- 1 P Laine, A Gourdon and J P Launay, *Inorg Chem*, 1995, **34**, 5129, 5138, 5156, 5150
- 2 A Cousson, F Nectoux, F Robert and E N Rizkalla, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1995, **C51**, 838, R E March, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1993, **C49**, 643
- 3 A Cousson, F Nectoux and E N Rizkalla, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1992, **C48**, 1354, K A Abboud, C Xu and R S Drago, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1998, **C54**, 1270
- 4 J F Hseu, J J Chen, C C Chuang, H H Wei, M C Cheng, R E March, Y Wang and Y D Yao, *Inorg Chim Acta*, 1991, **184**, 1, M Chatterjee, M Maji, S Ghosh and T C W Mak, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2917
- 5 D Ventur, K Weighardt and J Weiss *Z Anorg Allg Chem* 1985, **524**, 40
- 6 S K Chandra, P Chakraborty and A Chakraborty, *Proc Indian Acad Sci (Chem Sci)*, 1992, **104**, 351
- 7 L G Zhu, Y X Wang, C Y Duan, X S Yang, X S You and J S Huang, *Acta Chim Sinica*, 1992, **50**, 583
- 8 H Gainer, *J Org Chem*, 1959, **24**, 691
- 9 D M Adams and J B Raynor, "Advanced Practical Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley, London, 1965
- 10 G M Sheldrick, 1986, SHELXTL, Crystallographic System (Siemens Analytical Instrument Division, Madison)
- 11 D T Cromer and J T Waber, "International Tables for X-Ray Crystallography", Kynoch Press, Birmingham, 1974, Vol IV, Table 2 2
- 12 Ref 11, Vol IV, Table 2 3 1
- 13 G M Sheldrick, Shelxtl 96, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1990, **A46**, 467
- 14 R D Shannon, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1976, **A32**, 751